

List of satirists and satires

This is an incomplete list of writers, cartoonists and others known for involvement in satire—humorous social criticism. They are grouped by era and listed by year of birth. Included is a list of modern satires.

Early satirical authors

- Aesop (c. 620–560 BCE, Ancient Greece) – *Aesop's Fables*
- Diogenes (c. 412–600 BCE, Ancient Greece)
- Aristophanes (c. 448–380 BCE, Ancient Greece) – *The Frogs*, *The Birds*, and *The Clouds*
- Gaius Lucilius (c. 180–103 BCE, Roman Republic)
- Horace (65–8 BCE, Roman Republic) – *Satires*
- Ovid (43 BCE – 17 CE, Roman Republic/Roman Empire) – *The Art of Love*
- Seneca the Younger (c. 4 BCE – 65 CE, Hispania/Rome) – *Apocolocyntosis*
- Persius (34–62 CE, Roman Empire)
- Petronius (c. 27–66 CE, Roman Empire) – *Satyricon*
- Juvenal (1st to early 2nd cc. CE, Roman Empire) – *Satires*
- Lucian (c. 120–180 CE, Roman Empire)
- Apuleius (c. 123–180 CE, Roman Empire) – *The Golden Ass*
- *Various authors* (9th century CE and later) – *One Thousand and One Nights*, *ألف ليلة وليلة*

Medieval, early modern and 18th-century satirists

- Godfrey of Winchester (died 1107, England)
- Ubayd Zakani (عبيد زكاني, died 1370, Persia) – *Akhlaq al-Ashraf (Ethics of the Aristocracy)*
- Giovanni Boccaccio (1313–1375, Italy) – *The Decameron*
- James Bramston (1694–1743, England) – satirical poet
- Geoffrey Chaucer (c. 1343–1400, England) – *The Canterbury Tales*
- Sebastian Brant (also Brandt) (1458 – 1521, Strasbourg) – *Das Narrenschiff (Ship of Fools)*
- Gil Vicente (c. 1465–1536, Portugal)
- Erasmus (1466–1536, Burgundian Netherlands/Switzerland) – *The Praise of Folly*
- François Rabelais (c. 1493–1553, France) – *Gargantua and Pantagruel*
- *Various authors* (16th century CE and later, Italy) – *Talking statues of Rome*
- Miguel de Cervantes (1547–1616, Spain) – *Don Quixote*
- Luis de Góngora (1561–1627, Spain)
- William Shakespeare (1564–1616, England) – *Sonnet 130*
- Francisco de Quevedo (1580–1645, Spain)

- Juan de Tassis, 2nd Count of Villamediana (1582–1622, Spain)
- Martin Marprelate (true identity unknown, fl. 1588–1589, England) – *Marprelate tracts*
- Samuel Butler (1612–1680, England) – *Hudibras*
- Molière (1622–1673, France) – *Le Malade imaginaire*
- Margaret Cavendish, Duchess of Newcastle-upon-Tyne (1623–1673, England)
- John Wilmot, 2nd Earl of Rochester (1647–1680, England)
- Jonathan Swift (1667–1745, Ireland/England) – *Gulliver's Travels*, *A Modest Proposal*, *A Tale of a Tub*
- Alicia D'Anvers [née Clarke] (baptised 1668 – 1725, England) – *Academia, or, The Humours of the University of Oxford*, 1691; *The Oxford-Act*, 1693
- John Gay (1685–1732, England) – *The Beggar's Opera*
- Alexander Pope (1688–1744, England)
- Voltaire (1694–1778, France) – *Candide*
- James Bramston (1694–1744, England)
- William Hogarth (1697–1764, England) – *Beer Street and Gin Lane*
- Nicholas Amhurst (1697–1742, England)
- David Raphael ben Abraham Polido (fl. 17th and 18th cc.)
- Henry Fielding (1707–1754, England)
- Laurence Sterne (1713–1768, Ireland/England) – *The Life and Opinions of Tristram Shandy, Gentleman*
- James Beresford (1764–1840, England) – *The Miseries of Human Life*
- Ivan Krylov (1769–1844, Russia)
- Jane Austen (1775–1817, England) – *Love and Freindship*
- Thomas Love Peacock (1785–1866, England) – *Nightmare Abbey*, *Crochet Castle*
- Eaton Stannard Barrett (1786–1820, Ireland) – *The Heroine*
- Charles Etienne Boniface (1787–1853, France/South Africa) – *De Nieuwe Ridderorde of De Temperantisten* (in Dutch, *The New Knighthood or the Temperance Societies*)
- Giuseppe Gioachino Belli – (1791–1863, Italy)
- Benjamin Franklin - (1706-1790, US) - *Silence Dogood Letters*, *On Titles of Honor*, *The Busy-Body Letters*, *A Witch Trial at Mount Holly*, *Poor Richard's Almanack*, *Join, or Die*, *Felons and Rattlesnakes*, *The Speech of Polly Baker*, *On the Slave-Trade*

Modern satirists (born 1800–1900)

- Evan Bevan (1803–1866, Wales) – satirical poetry in Welsh
- Nikolai Gogol (1809–1852, Russia) – *The Government Inspector*, *Dead Souls*
- Edgar Allan Poe (1809–1849, US) – *The Man That Was Used Up*, *A Predicament*, *Never Bet the Devil Your Head*
- William Makepeace Thackeray (1811–1863, England) – *Vanity Fair*
- Charles Dickens (1812–1870, England) – *Hard Times*, *A Tale of Two Cities*
- Eugène Edine Pottier (1816–1887, France)
- James Russell Lowell (1819–1891, US) – *A Fable for Critics*
- George Derby, also known as John P. Squibob and John Phoenix (1823–1861, US)

- Mikhail Saltykov-Shchedrin (1826–1889, Russia)
- Lewis Carroll (1832–1898, England) – *Alice in Wonderland*, *Through the Looking Glass*
- Samuel Butler (1835–1902, England) – *Erewhon*
- Mark Twain (1835–1910, US) – *Adventures of Huckleberry Finn*, *A Connecticut Yankee in King Arthur's Court*, *The Celebrated Jumping Frog of Calaveras County*
- W. S. Gilbert (1836–1911, England)
- Narushima Ryūhoku (成島柳北, 1837–1884, Japan)
- Thomas Nast (1840–1902, US)
- Ambrose Bierce (1842 – c. 1914, US) – *The Devil's Dictionary*
- Anatole France (1844–1924, France)
- José Maria de Eça de Queirós (1845–1900, Portugal)
- Oscar Wilde (1854–1900, Ireland/England) – *The Importance of Being Earnest*
- George Bernard Shaw (1856–1950, England)
- Jerome K. Jerome (1859–1927, England) – *Three Men in a Boat, Idle Thoughts of an Idle Fellow*
- Anton Chekhov (1860–1904, Russia) – *The Lady with the Dog*
- O. Henry (1862–1910, US) short story writer known for surprise endings, namesake of the O. Henry Award
- Jalil Mammadguluzadeh (1866–1931, Azerbaijan)
- Lakshminath Bezbaroa (1868–1938, India, writing in Assamese)
- Saki, also known as H. H. Munro (1870–1916, England)
- Trilussa (1873–1950, Italy)
- Alfred Jarry (1873–1907, France) – *Ubu Roi*
- Radoje Domanović (1873–1908, Serbia)
- Iraj Mirza (1926–1874, ایرج میرزا, Iran)
- Karl Kraus (1874–1936, Austria)
- Will Rogers (1879–1935, US)
- James Branch Cabell (1879–1958, US)
- Ali-Akbar Dehkhoda (1959–1879, علی‌اکبر دهخدا, Iran)
- H. L. Mencken (1880–1956, US) – cultural critic and author
- Arkady Averchenko (1881–1925, Russia)
- P. G. Wodehouse (1881–1975, England/US)
- Wyndham Lewis (1882–1957, England)
- Jaroslav Hašek (1883–1923, Austria-Hungary/Czechoslovakia) – *The Good Soldier Švejk*
- Oscar Cesare (1885–1948, Sweden/US)
- Charlie Chaplin (1889-1977, England) – *Modern Times*, *The Great Dictator*, *Monsieur Verdoux*
- Kurt Tucholsky (1890–1935, Germany)
- Mikhail Bulgakov (1891–1940, Russia/Soviet Union) – *Heart of a Dog*, *The Master and Margarita*
- Dorothy Parker (1893–1967, US) satirical writer of humorous short stories, poetry and book reviews
- Vladimir Mayakovsky (1893–1930, Russia/Soviet Union)

- Aldous Huxley (1894–1963) – *Point Counter Point*, *Brave New World*
- James Thurber (1894–1961, US) – "The Secret Life of Walter Mitty"
- Mikhail Zoshchenko (1894–1958, Soviet Union)
- Josep Pla (1897–1981, Spain [Catalonia])
- Ilf and Petrov: Ilya Ilf (1897–1937, Soviet Union) and Yevgeni Petrov (1903–1942, Soviet Union) – *The Twelve Chairs*, *The Little Golden Calf*
- Yury Olesha (1899–1960, Soviet Union) – *Three Fat Men*, *Envy*

Modern satirists (born 1900–1930)

- Stella Gibbons (1902–1989, England) – author of comic novel *Cold Comfort Farm*
- Evelyn Waugh (1903–1966, England) – *Brideshead Revisited*, *Decline and Fall*, *Scoop*
- George Orwell (1903–1950, England) – *Animal Farm*, *Nineteen Eighty-Four*
- Malcolm Muggeridge (1903–1990, England)
- Dr. Seuss (1904–1991, US) – *The Lorax* (1971), *The Butter Battle Book* (1984)
- Kurt Kusenberg (1904–1983, Germany)
- Daniil Kharms (1905–1942, Russia/USSR)
- H. F. Ellis (1907–2000, England) – *The Papers of A. J. Wentworth, B.A.*, 1949
- Jean Effel (1908–1982, France) – cartoonist, author of the cartoon cycle *The Creation of the World*
- Natyaguru Nurul Momen (1908–1990, Bangladesh) - pioneer satirist & playwright, author of *We are Brothers All*, *Lest we Forget*, *Forbidden Pleasures*, *Bahurupa*, *Is Law an Ass* etc.
- Al Capp (1909–1979, US)
- Arkady Raikin (1911–1987, Russia/USSR) – stand-up comedian
- Aubrey Menen (1912–1989, Britain, India) – satirist, novelist and philosopher
- Walt Kelly (1913–1973, US)
- Anthony Burgess (1917–1993, England) – *A Clockwork Orange*
- Warrington Colescott (1921–2018, US)
- Kurt Vonnegut (1922–2007, US) – *Slaughterhouse-Five*, *Breakfast of Champions*, *Cat's Cradle*
- Lenny Bruce (1925–1966, US) – stand-up comedian
- Joseph Heller (1923–1999, US) – *Catch-22*
- Art Buchwald (1924–2007) – political humor column in *The Washington Post*
- Terry Southern (1924–1995, US) – *The Magic Christian*, *Dr. Strangelove*
- Günter Grass (1927–2015, Germany) – *The Tin Drum*, *Cat and Mouse*
- Stanley Kubrick (1928–1999, US) – *Dr. Strangelove*
- Harvey Kurtzman (1924–1993, US)
- Tom Lehrer (born 1928, US) – *That Was the Year That Was*
- Jules Feiffer (1929, US) – satirical cartoonist who wrote the original play and screenplay for *Little Murders*
- Ray Bradbury (US)
- William S. Burroughs (US) – *Naked Lunch*

- Dario Fo (Italy)
- Flannery O'Connor (US)
- C. Northcote Parkinson (England)
- Anna Russell (England/Canada)
- Gore Vidal (US) – *Myra Breckinridge*
- Mel Brooks (US) – *The Producers*, *Blazing Saddles*, *Young Frankenstein*
- Erma Bombeck (1927, US)
- Allan Sherman (1924–1973, US) – musician, parodist, television producer, voice actor
- Stan Freberg (1926, US) – musician, parodist, voice actor
- Brian O'Nolan (1911–1966, Ireland) – *At Swim-Two-Birds* (as Flann O'Brien)
- Ephraim Kishon (1924, Israel)
- Jerry Lewis (1926-2017) (US) – comedian, screenwriter, director

Contemporary satirists (born 1930–1960)

- Joey Skaggs (born 1945, US) - artist and media satirist
- Mordecai Richler (1931–2001, Canada)
- Tom Wolfe (born 1931, US) – *The Bonfire of the Vanities*
- Vladimir Voinovich (born 1932, Soviet Union/Russia) – *The Life and Extraordinary Adventures of Private Ivan Chonkin*, *Moscow 2042*
- Robert Anton Wilson (1932–2007, US) – *The Illuminatus! Trilogy*
- Barry Humphries (1934–2023, Australia) – *My Gorgeous Life*, *The Life and Death of Sandy Stone*, stage shows
- Jonathan Miller (1934–2019, England)
- Alan Bennett (born 1934, England)
- Mykhailo Zhvanetskyi (born 1934, Soviet Union/Russia)
- Dudley Moore (1935–2002, England)
- David Lodge (born 1935, US) – author of "Campus Trilogy"
- Woody Allen (born 1935, US)
- Thomas Pynchon (born 1937, US) – *V.*, *The Crying of Lot 49*, *Gravity's Rainbow*
- Richard Ingrams (born 1937, England)
- John Kennedy O'Toole (born 1937, US)
- George Carlin (1937–2008, US) – stand-up comedian
- Peter Cook (1937–1995, England) – of the *Satire boom*, *Beyond the Fringe*
- Eleanor Bron (born 1938, England)
- David Frost (1939–2013, England)
- Grigori Gorin (1940–2000, Soviet Union/Russia)
- Frank Zappa (1940–1993, US) – *We're Only in It for the Money*, *Cruising with Ruben and the Jets*
- Sergei Dovlatov (1941–1990, Soviet Union/Russia)
- Kioumars Saberi Foumani (2004–1941, کیمورث صابری فومنی, Iran)
- Randy Newman (born 1943, US) - *Sail Away*, *Good Old Boys*

- Neil Innes (1944–2019, England) – former Bonzo Dog Doo-Dah Band founder and member of The Rutles. Writer of satirical songs and books
- Gennady Khazanov (born 1945, Soviet Union/Russia) – stand-up comedian
- Luba Goy (born 1945, Canada)
- Roger Abbott (born 1946, Canada) – sketch comedian.
- Lewis Grizzard (born 1946, US)
- Sue Townsend (1946–2014, England) – Adrian Mole
- Don Ferguson (born 1946, Canada)
- Jonathan Meades (born 1947, England) – writer, broadcaster and satirist
- P.J. O'Rourke (1947-2022, US)
- Terry Pratchett (1948–2015) – humorist and fantasy novelist, The Discworld book series
- Lewis Black (born 1948, US) – stand-up comic, The Daily Show
- Mikhail Zadornov (born 1948, Soviet Union/Russia)
- Garry Trudeau (born 1948, US)
- Jaafar Abbas (living, Sudan)
- Christopher Guest (born 1948, US) – This Is Spinal Tap, Waiting for Guffman
- Georg Schramm (born 1949, Germany) – Scheibenwischer, Neues aus der Anstalt, kabarett artist
- Gary Larson (born 1950, US) – cartoonist
- Fran Lebowitz (born 1950, US) – The Fran Lebowitz Reader, Public Speaking (film) – NYC public intellectual
- Bailey White (born 1950, US)
- Joe Queenan (born 1950, US)
- Steve Bell (born 1951, England)
- Bill Bryson (born 1951, US)
- Al Franken (born 1951, US)
- Douglas Adams (1952–2001, England) – The Hitchhiker's Guide to the Galaxy
- Mary Walsh (born 1952, Canada)
- Phil Hendrie (born 1952, US) – radio host of The Phil Hendrie Show
- Robert Zubrin (born 1952, US)
- Christopher Buckley (born 1952) – Thank You for Smoking, The White House Mess
- Carl Hiaasen (born 1953) – Tourist Season, Double Whammy, Basket Case, Skinny Dip
- Stoney Burke (born 1953, US)
- Louis de Bernières (born 1954, UK) – Latin America Trilogy: The War of Don Emmanuel's Nether Parts, Señor Vivo and the Coca Lord, The Troublesome Offspring of Cardinal Guzman
- Matt Groening (born 1954, US) – The Simpsons, Futurama
- George C. Wolfe (born 1954, US) – The Colored Museum
- Howard Stern (born 1954, US)
- Jaspal Bhatti (1955–2012, India)
- Cathy Jones (born 1955, Canada)
- Bill Maher (born 1956, US) – Real Time with Bill Maher
- Percival Everett (born 1956, US)

- Ziad Rahbani (زيد الرحباني, born 1956, Lebanon)
- David Sedaris (born 1956, US) – *Naked, Me Talk Pretty One Day*
- Craig Brown (born 1957, UK)
- Scott Adams (born 1957, US) – *Dilbert*
- Stephen Fry (born 1957, England)
- Christopher Moore (born 1957, US)
- Victor Shenderovich (born 1958, Russia)
- Ebrahim Nabavi (سيد ابراهيم نبوى, born 1958, Iran), winner of Prince Claus Award (2005)
- Bill Watterson (born 1958, US) – cartoonist, *Calvin and Hobbes*
- Jello Biafra (born 1958, US)
- George Saunders (born 1958, US) – author of *CivilWarLand In Bad Decline*, *Tenth of December* and *Lincoln in the Bardo*.
- Wayne Federman (born 1959, US)
- "Weird Al" Yankovic (born 1959, US)
- Hugh Laurie (born 1959, England)
- Jeffrey Morgan (living, Canada) – CREEM, Metro Times
- Denis Leary (born 1957, US)

Contemporary satirists (born 1960–present)

In alphabetical order (many birth dates not known):

- Jacob M. Appel (US, born 1973) – playwright (*Causa Mortis, Arborophilia*)
- Michael "Atters" Attree (born 1965, UK)
- Max Barry (born 1973, Australia) – author
- Paul Beatty (born 1962, US) – (*The White Boy Shuffle*, *The Sellout*)
- Nigel Blackwell (living, UK) – *Half Man Half Biscuit*
- Jan Böhmermann (born 1981, Germany)
- Charlie Brooker (born 1971, UK) – *Nathan Barley*
- Bo Burnham (born 1990, US) – comedian and musician
- Dave Chappelle (born 1973, US) – stand-up comedian, *Chappelle's Show*
- David Cross (born 1964, US) – *Mr. Show*, *Arrested Development*
- Sacha Baron Cohen (born 1971) – *Borat*, *Da Ali G Show*
- Stephen Colbert (born 1964, US) – *The Colbert Report*, *The Daily Show*
- Sarah Cooper (born 1977, US) – blogger, vlogger, author, comedian
- Douglas Coupland (born 1961, Canada) – *Generation X: Tales for an Accelerated Culture*
- Scott Dikkers (born 1965, US) – comedy writer and speaker
- Bret Easton Ellis (born 1964, US) – screenwriter and director
- Ricky Gervais (born 1961, UK) – comedian, creator of *The Office* (British TV series)
- Sabina Guzzanti (born 1963, Italy) – satirist and writer
- Bill Hicks (1961–1994, US) – stand-up comedian
- Mishu Hilmy (living, US) – *Good Morning Gitmo*

- Ian Hislop (born 1960, UK) – *Private Eye*
- Jessica Holmes (born 1973, Canada) – comedian and actress
- Armando Iannucci (born 1963, UK) – *Brass Eye*, *The Day Today*
- Mike Judge (born 1962, US) – creator of *Beavis and Butt-Head* and *King of the Hill*
- Elnathan John (born 1982, Nigeria) — *Be(com)ing Nigerian: A Guide*
- Kennedy (born 1972, US) – radio personality and author
- Hari Kondabolu (born 1982, US) – stand-up comic and film-maker
- Erik Larsen (born 1962, US) – "Savage Dragon" comic book
- Craig Lauzon (living, Canada) – comedian and caricaturist
- Stewart Lee (born 1968, UK) – stand-up comedian and director
- Victor Lewis-Smith (living, UK) – *TV Offal*
- Chris Lilley (born 1974, Australia) – *Summer Heights High*, *We Can Be Heroes: Finding The Australian of the Year*
- Daniele Luttazzi (born 1961, Italy) – satirist and songwriter
- Maddox (born 1978, US) – website *The Best Page in the Universe*
- Seth MacFarlane (born 1973, US) – *Family Guy*
- Aaron McGruder (US) – *The Boondocks (comic strip)*, *The Boondocks (TV series)*
- Rick Mercer (born 1969, Canada) – *Rick Mercer Report*
- Tim Minchin (born 1975, Australia) – comedian and musician

- Mark Morford (living, US) – *Notes and Errata*, *San Francisco Chronicle*, *SF Gate*
- Chris Morris (born 1965, UK) – *Brass Eye*, *The Day Today*
- Gregory Motton (born 1961, UK) – playwright and author
- The Moustache Brothers (Myanmar) – screwball comedy and dance
- Bob Odenkirk (born 1962, US) – *Mr. Show*, *Saturday Night Live*, *The Larry Sanders Show*
- John Oliver (born 1977, England) – *Last Week Tonight with John Oliver*^[1]
- Chuck Palahniuk (born 1962, US) – *Fight Club* and *Choke*
- Alan Park (born 1962, Canada) – comedian and satirist
- Trey Parker (born 1969, US) – *South Park*, *Team America: World Police*, *The Book of Mormon*
- Alexandra Petri (born 1988, US) – author and columnist
- Mark A. Rayner (living, Canada) – satirist and fiction writer
- Pablo Reyes Jr. (born 1989, US) – website *The Daily Currant* and *Huzlers*
- Celia Rivenbark (living, US) – columnist and author
- Joe Rogan (born 1967, US) – comedian and podcast pioneer
- Eric Schwartz (living, US) – folk singer and satirist
- Andrew Shaffer (living, US) – author
- Amy Sedaris (born 1961, US) – actress and comedian
- Sarah Silverman (born 1970, US) – stand-up comedian, *The Sarah Silverman Program*
- Martin Sonneborn (born 1965, Germany) – political jokester and satirist
- Jon Stewart (born 1962, US) – *The Daily Show*
- Matt Stone (born 1971, US) – *South Park*, *The Book of Mormon*
- Vermin Supreme (born 1961, US) – performance artist, comedian and political satirist

- Greg Thomey (born 1961, Canada) – comedian and playwright
- David Thorne (living, Australia) – humorist and satirist
- Andrew Unger, (living, Canada) – Mennonite satirist
- Jhonen Vasquez (born 1974, US) – *Johnny the Homicidal Maniac*, *Squee*
- Oliver Welke (born 1966, Germany) - *heute-show*
- Mark Whitney (born 1959, US) – satirist and comedian
- Howard X, (living, Hong Kong, Australia) – political satirist, musician, professional impersonator of Kim Jong-un
- Bassem Youssef (باسم رأفت محمد يوسف, born 1974, Egypt) – comedian
- Rucka Rucka Ali (born 1987, Israel) – political satirist, song parody maker
- Dr. Suresh Kumar Mishra 'Uratript' (born 1981, India) – humorist and satirist.^[2]

Notable satires in contemporary popular culture

In modern culture, much satire is often the work of several individuals collectively, as in magazines and television. Hence the following list.

Print

- Astérix (French comic strip, satirizing both the Roman Empire era as well as 20th century life)
- Benchley (US comic strip created by Mort Drucker and Jerry Dumas, satirizing Ronald Reagan and American culture)
- Bone (US comic strip)
- The Boondocks (US comic strip, satirizing African-American culture)
- Le Canard enchaîné (weekly French satirical newspaper)
- Charlie Hebdo (weekly French satirical paper)
- The Chaser (Australian newspaper and TV shows)
- Cho Ramaswamy (Thuglak – Tamil magazine)
- Craposyncrasies (Persian book)
- Dilbert (US comic strip)
- The Donald Duck and Uncle Scrooge comics by Carl Barks
- Doonesbury (US comic strip)
- The Fabulous Furry Freak Brothers (US comic strip)
- Faux Faulkner contest (annually published in *Hemispheres* magazine until 2005)
- Fritz the Cat by Robert Crumb
- Humor Times (monthly US magazine)
- Idées noires (Belgian comic strip)
- Li'l Abner (US comic strip)
- Life in Hell (US comic strip)
- Mad (satirical comic book and magazine)

- The Medium (weekly newspaper printed by students of Rutgers University)
- Mr. Natural by Robert Crumb
- Nero (Belgian comic strip)
- The New Yorker (Shouts and Murmurs)
- The Onion (US magazine)
- Peanuts (US comic strip)
- Pogo (US comic strip)
- Private Eye (UK magazine)
- The Inconsequential (UK magazine)
- The Second Supper (US magazine)
- The Tart (Fortnightly UK newspaper)
- The Adventures of Tintin (Belgian comic strip)
- Titanic (German magazine)
- Tom Puss (Dutch comic strip)
- Wild Wise Weird (Vietnamese satirical fables)^{[3][4]}
- Watchmen (American comic book series)

Television and radio

- The Simpsons and Futurama (Matt Groening)
- Howard Stern (radio personality "The Howard Stern Show")
- The Daily Show with Jon Stewart (US Talk Show)
- The Colbert Report (US Talk Show)
- The Day Today (UK TV news parody by Chris Morris)
- Brass Eye (UK current affairs TV-show parody by Chris Morris)
- On the Hour (UK news radio parody by Chris Morris)
- TV Offal (UK TV critique show by Victor Lewis-Smith)
- This Hour Has 22 Minutes (Canadian TV show)
- South Park (Trey Parker and Matt Stone)
- The Chaser (Australian newspaper and TV shows)
- Facelift (New Zealand Political show)
- Spitting Image (UK TV show famous for its puppets of celebrities)
- Yes Minister (also "Yes, Prime Minister" – UK TV show satirising government)
- Kukly (*Dolls*, 1994–2002) – Russian satirical puppet show
- Fitul (*Fuse*) – Soviet television satirical/comedy short film series
- Nip/Tuck (Ryan Murphy)
- Have I Got News For You – Long running UK TV panel show
- Nathan Barley – 2005 UK TV satire by Chris Morris and Charlie Brooker.
- The Chaser's War on Everything – Australian satire with an emphasis on attacking 'everyone'.
- Seinfeld (Jerry Seinfeld)
- Royal Canadian Air Farce (1993–2007) (Don Ferguson, Roger Abbott, Luba Goy)

- Air Farce Live (2007–present) (Don Ferguson, Roger Abbott, Luba Goy)
- Monty Python's Flying Circus
- Phil Hendrie (radio personality "The Phil Hendrie Show")
- Mock the Week – UK TV comedy panel show
- The Larry Sanders Show – (Garry Shandling)
- 30 Rock – (Tina Fey)
- Glenn Martin, DDS – A Nick@Nite show
- Episodes – David Crane
- Better Off Ted – (Victor Fresco)
- Onion News Network
- The Boondocks – (Aaron McGruder)
- heute-show (German TV series)
- Servant of the People (2015 TV series) — Ukrainian political satire comedy TV series starring Volodymyr Zelensky
- The Amazing World of Gumball – Ben Bocquelet
- Family Guy – (Seth MacFarlane)
- On Cinema at the Cinema – (Tim Heidecke), Gregg Turkington)
- The Fresh Prince of Bel-Air – (Andy Borowitz and Susan Borowitz)

Music

- The Cover of "Rolling Stone" a satirical lament by Dr. Hook & the Medicine Show.
- "White America" is a satirical song by Eminem It is about his impact in rap and the impact of rap in the white communities.
- "Mercedes Benz" is a McClure-Joplin song sung by Janis Joplin
- Culturcide's album *Tacky Souvenirs of Pre-Revolutionary America* overdubbed new, satirical lyrics onto such pop hits as "We Are the World".
- Vaporwave, a satirical music genre with anarcho-capitalist and cyberpunk overtones dedicated to (anti-)consumerism.^[5]
- Mark Russell is an American political satirist known for his many appearances on PBS
- Peter Gabriel's song *The Barry Williams Show* satirizes talk shows which showcase domestic topics of a taboo or shocking nature (and the viewing public's fascination with such content).
- Chumbawamba have consistently used satire to make political points throughout their musical career.
- Pink Floyd's albums *Animals* and *The Dark Side of the Moon* are conceptual and satirical albums.
- The Lonely Island is a satirical music group known for their work on Saturday Night Live.
- Trey Parker, Robert Lopez and Matt Stone's Tony-sweeping Broadway show The Book of Mormon (musical) satirizes the applicability of first-world religion to third-world problems.
- The Dead Milkmen is a satirical punk rock/cowpunk band from the early 1980s.
- Ben Folds, a rock pianist, and his group, Ben Folds Five, have multiple songs including satirical elements. Some of them being, "Underground", "Sports and Wine", and "Rock Star".

- Dead Kennedys, an American punk band, often used satire in their songs, most notably Kill the Poor.
- Frank Zappa and the Mothers of Invention's We're Only in It for the Money, a satire of flower power and conservative America.

Film

- Blazing Saddles, a 1974 comedy movie directed by Mel Brooks, satirizing racism
- Casino Royale, a 1967 surrealistic satire on the James Bond series and the entire spy genre.
- Get Out
- This Is Spinal Tap, a satire on heavy metal culture and "rockumentaries"
- The Very Same Munchhausen, a 1979 satire of the late Soviet society
- Clueless
- American Beauty, a 1999 satire of life in the suburbs
- Thank You for Smoking
- Team America: World Police is a 2004 film satirizing Hollywood action flicks as well as post-9/11 American foreign policy.
- Wag the Dog
- The Rules of Attraction
- Best in Show
- I Heart Huckabees
- Starship Troopers
- Scary Movie
- Donald Trump's The Art of the Deal: The Movie^[6]
- Dr. Strangelove
- Planet of the Apes
- South Park: Bigger, Longer & Uncut, a film satirizing censorship
- Network
- Otaku no Video, a 1993 anime satirizing the otaku subculture
- Adaptation.
- Brazil
- S.O.B., a satire on Hollywood.
- Election
- Not Another Teen Movie, a satire of the teen film genre
- Harold & Kumar Go to White Castle
- Harold & Kumar Escape from Guantanamo Bay
- Citizen Ruth
- The Hospital
- Weapons of Mass Distraction
- Little Children
- Bulworth
- Man Bites Dog

- *The Simpsons Movie*
- *Smile*, a satire of beauty pageants and small-town life
- *Bob Roberts*
- *War, Inc.*
- *Britannia Hospital*
- *Fight Club*, a dark satire on consumerism, cults, and extremism
- *American Psycho*
- *Tropic Thunder*
- *Simon*, satirical commentary on the effects of mass media in pop culture
- *American History X* satirizes race/racism in a contemporary setting
- *They Live*
- *Land of the Dead*, a satire of post-9/11 America state and of the Bush administration
- *The Wicker Man*, a satire on cults and religion
- *The Great Dictator*, a satire on Adolf Hitler
- *Monty Python's Life of Brian*, a satire on miscommunication, religion and Christianity
- *The Player*, a satire of Hollywood, directed by Robert Altman
- *In the Loop*, a satire of the 2003 invasion of Iraq
- *Elvis Gratton*, a French Canadian/Québécois series depicting a satirical federalist
- *Fubar*
- *The Man Who Knew Too Little*

Video games

- *Fallout*
- *Fallout 2*
- *Fallout 3*
- *Fallout: New Vegas*
- *Fallout 4*
- *Dead Rising* (デッドライジング, *Deddo Raijingu*), a satire on US consumer culture
- *Dead Rising 2: Off the Record* (デッドライジング2 オフ・ザ・レコード, *Deddo Raijingu 2: Ofu za rekōdo*), a satire on US consumer culture
- *Grand Theft Auto*^[7]
- *Crash: Mind over Mutant*^[8]

Internet

- Adequacy.org
- The Babylon Bee (Christian satire)
- BBspot
- The Best Page In The Universe
- BuyTigers.com
- Coconut Kelz (South African satirical video blogger)

- [The Daily Mash](#) (U.K. satirical news website)
- [The Daily Bonnet](#) (Mennonite satire website)
- [Faking News](#) (Indian news satire website)
- [The Hard Times](#)
- [Huzlers](#)
- [Landover Baptist Church](#) (US website satirizing Fundamentalist Christians)
- [Latma](#)
- [McSweeney's Internet Tendency](#)
- [The Montgonion](#)
- [National Report](#)
- [Jeremy Nell](#) (South African cartoonist)
- [NewsBiscuit](#)
- [The Onion](#)
- [Pat Condell](#)
- [Reductress](#)
- [ScrappleFace](#)
- [Sorry Everybody](#)
- [The Second Supper](#)
- [The UnReal Times](#) (Indian news satire website)
- [Uncyclopedia](#) (satirical parody of Wikipedia)
- [Vote for the Worst](#)

See also

- [List of satirical news websites](#)

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